

Figure 2A

Figure 2B

72kDa
50kDa
40kDa

PDCD4
(52KDa)

72kDa
50kDa
40kDa

IGF2BP3
(64KDa)

72kDa
50kDa
40kDa

actin
(42KDa)

Control
OGD
OGD+vector
OGD+DZI

Figure 2A

Figure 3D

30kDa
25kDa
20kDa
15kDa
10kDa

Bax
(21kDa)

72kDa
50kDa
40kDa

actin
(42kDa)

A B C D

40kDa
30kDa
25kDa
20kDa

Bcl2
(26kDa)

50kDa
40kDa
30kDa
25kDa
20kDa
15kDa

Cleaved-
caspase3
(17,19,32-
35kDa)

A: Control
B: OGD
C: OGD+sh-NC
D: OGD+sh-IGF2BP3

A B C D

Figure 4A

PDCD4
(52KDa)

actin
(42KDa)

A B C D

A: Control
B: OGD
C: OGD+sh-NC
D: OGD+sh-IGF2BP3

Figure 4B

72kDa
50kDa
40kDa

IGF2BP3

Input IgG IP IGF2BP3

Figure 5A

72kDa
50kDa
40kDa

PDCD4
(52KDa)

72kDa
50kDa
40kDa

actin
(42KDa)

A B C D

A: OGD+vector
B: OGD+DZ
C: OGD+DZ+oe-NC
D: OGD+DZ+oe-IGF2BP3)

Figure 5D

30kDa
25KDa
20kDa
15kDa
10kDa

Bax
(21KDa)

72kDa
50kDa
40kDa

actin
(42KDa)

A B C D

40kDa
30kDa
25KDa
20kDa
15kDa

Bcl2
(26KDa)

50kDa
40kDa
30KDa
25kDa
20kDa
15kDa

Cleaved-
caspase3
(17,19,32-
35KDa)

A B C D

A: OGD+vector
B: OGD+DZ
C: OGD+DZ+oe-NC
D: OGD+DZ+oe-IGF2BP3